

Sugarcamp Project, Putnam County

Since construction in 2022, the Sugarcamp Project has received both point source (septic tank) and nonpoint source (tile drain) inflows, which help maintain a consistent water level and nutrient source in the Main Pool even under drought conditions. Throughout 2024, the Main Pool outflow often had no flow, indicating much of the nutrient input was stored and not exported. The Vernal Pool and the hummock and hollow pools are variable in their water storage and resulting potential to retain nutrients. The Project's known nutrient benefit also includes runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.6 lbs of phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is passively managed. The Project has 9 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a flow-through wetland system as well as around 50 hummock and hollow pools within a floodplain wetland. The Main Pool has four inflows that flow into the pool before discharging into a ditch flowing into the Blanchard River. Two of the inflows are surface water runoff; one directs water from the hummock and hollow portion of the wetland and the other drains from an agricultural field to the east. The other two inflows are tile drainage from surrounding areas. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which the Blanchard River floods its banks filling the hummock and hollow pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
9 acres	0.6 lbs	19 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.